

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF RESOURCE CONSTRAINTS ON VISIBLE POLICING AND DETECTIVE WORK AT HILLBROW POLICE STATION FROM 2018 TO 2021.

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Abstract

The impact of resources is relevant to the modern South African Police Service (SAPS) given the spotlight which SAPS has in the public domain with regards to the expectations and the drawbacks emanating from the souring statistics of low crime detection and conviction rates. Several crime researchers have argued that a lack of adequate resources to fight crime may be responsible. It is therefore of paramount importance to assess the extent to which the lack of resources has hindered are the SAPS ability to fight crime effectively. The aim and objectives of the research are: to determine the extent of impact of resource constraints on detective and visible policing functions at Hillbrow Police Station, to establish different types of resources which SAPS need to execute their duties, to establish the impact of resource constraints on police work; and to establish ways of increasing productivity using limited resources. The study showed that although the identified resources constraints are a major factor in the increase of crime in Hillbrow, however, other factors were also identified as also contributors to the increase in crime levels. These include social issues like street kids, challenges faced by the justice system, municipalities, and home affairs in controlling the influx of illegal immigrants in the country it is found that the resources constraints account for the main challenge in the fight against crime.

Keywords: Police, resources, detectives, Visible Policing, Service Delivery.

INTRODUCTION

The SAPS derives its mandate from Section 205 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996; the objects of policing are to -prevent, combat, and investigate crime; maintain public order; protect and secure the inhabitants of the Republic and their property; and uphold and enforce the law. (Service, 2020). Ideally police and policing should be performed by highly qualified individuals, supported by the best tools and resources, discharged with the highest professional standards that produce good and accountable managerial results that best serve the people (Husselmann, 2017). The statistics of crime in South Africa have continued to increase despite the commitment of Government to curb the pandemic raising questions on the causes of failure, one area widely given attention being availability of resources. This research is aimed at assessing the extent of the damage caused by resource constraints in SAPS with reference to Hillbrow Police Station.

Background to the problem

Hillbrow is one of the most densely populated neighbourhoods in the City of Johannesburg with an estimated (1) one million residents accommodated in about two hundred (200) high-rise apartment blocks within an area of one point five square per kilometre (1.5km²) (City of Johannesburg 2009). Furthermore, residential occupation in this area has increased by more than two-fold within twenty (20) years (i.e., between 1989 and 2009). From such an increase which

has continued to rise to date hence overcrowding, pressure on resources like hospitals and police station has continued to unwanted levels. According to the 2019/20 crime statistics, Hillbrow ranks third (3rd) in contact crimes with four thousand, four hundred and forty-five (4 445) cases; an increase from the previous financial year of four thousand, three hundred and thirty-four (4 334). This therefore calls for well-resourced law enforcement and strategies to curb the criminal activities in the area.

Problem statement

Resource constrains is one of the problems cited when explaining high crime statistics. This research proposal aims to determine the impact of resource constraint if any in curbing crime through visible policing and detective work during the period 2018 to 2021.

Sub-problems

The research tries to determine if resource constraints are the only explanation for current level of Police performance. The sub-problems identified are as follows:

- a) Human Resources.
- b) Budget Constraints.
- c) Shortage of vehicles.
- d) Detectives Skills Training.
- e) Lack of proper procurement processes; and
- f) Technology Constraints.

Research Questions

- What extent does availability of resources affect performance of Police Officers?

- What other factors other than resources affect performance of Police Officers?
- What strategies can be implemented to improve performance despite limited resources?
- What is the best methodology to measure performance?

Resources Constraints in Hillbrow police station has had a significant impact on the work of visible policing and detective. The following is the summary of the main results and conclusions of the impact of these constraints:

Human Resources - The results showed that the main constraint is personnel. As Hillbrow community has grown significantly, more visible police and detectives are needed. There are staff shortages that are because of members retiring and resigning to joint other professions but have not been replaced. The results further showed that only four (4) shifts in Crime Prevention are servicing over (R1) one million rands community. The shortage has resulted in increased workload for police officers. Where there is an increased workload police officers starts to suffer from fatigue, burn-out, stress, and reduced morale. When the members are unwell, this has a negative impact on their output.

Budget Constraints - There are constraints that result from budget cuts on the national level which has a ripple effect in the functioning at provincial level and station level. Budget constraint have affected the personnel turnover, procurement of personal protective equipment (PPE), ammunition, evidence kits, pepper sprays, dagga weighing scales with calibration certificate, police handheld radios and many more. These have negatively impacted the capacity of visible policing and detectives to conduct investigations due to the following factors:

1. **Shortage of vehicles** - the findings showed that the main resource constraint affecting both visible policing and detectives is the availability motor vehicles that are in good mechanical working order. The station does not have enough supply of vehicles. This results in police officers having to share vehicles and borrow from other shifts. Some vehicles breakdowns constantly and the turnaround time to fix them can take up to six (6) months due to the backlog at the police garage. This in turn affect visible policing and detective work because if members have no means for transport, they cannot do proper patrolling work or respond to emergency calls. The detectives cannot travel with ease to the crime scenes and to conduct their investigation. The shortage of vehicles leads to a reduction in the number of police officers on patrol. This in turn negatively affect visible policing. When there is no police visibility, the public confidence in the police decrease and the fear of crime increases.

2. **Detectives Skills Training** - Some detectives lack the necessary skills in investigation of specific crimes that has increased in the community like, murder, cybercrime, domestic violence, and crimes involving children. It is important that detectives are trained adequately in the specialized crime investigation. This training should include crime scene preservation, collection of evidence, preserving evidence, etc. If the de-

tectives are not adequately trained, they become ineffective in their fight against crime. The fight against crime cannot be won if perpetrators are acquitted because of lack of evidence.

3. **Lack of proper procurement processes** - The results demonstrated that constraints seen in the procurement department has contributed immensely on the challenges faced by both the visible police and detectives. The station currently has a shortage of blue lights in the police vehicles. This hampers the fight against crime because even if a police vehicle s patrolling, community members cannot identify that it's a police vehicle. Blue lights also help to deter criminals from committing crime if they see the presence of police. The other constraints caused by poor procurement processes is that there is no Morpho Touch, fingerprint checking machine which was helping the visible police members to clean out the streets. There is also shortage in the procurement of Bullet Proof Vests. this is putting the safety of police officers at risk when they are outside fighting crime.

4. **Technology Constraints** - technology constraints also play a big part in the fight against crime. There is a lack of advanced technology at the station level such as forensic labs and surveillance equipment. The detectives must rely on the main lab at the head office which is also having a backlog. This causes the investigation of crime to take too long and leads to reduced public trust. Another example of technical challenges is the availability of a system that will allow visible police officers body camera that will record the activities of the police officers and transmit the images and audio.

5. **Resource constraints** in SAPS have a significant impact on visible policing and detective work at Hillbrow Police Station. South Africa faces numerous crime related challenges which include high levels of violent crime, organized crime, cybercrime, violence against women and children, and widespread corruption. The research demonstrated that here is shortage in human resource, there are budget constraints, shortage of vehicles, gaps in the training of detective skills, lack of working procurement processes and that there are technology problems in the national forensic laboratory. All these factors limit the ability of the visible police and detectives to provide effective policing services. Preventing and solving crime abilities are also negatively affected.

6. It is important for South African Police Service to address these constraints in order to ensure that visible police and detectives are able to carry out their mandate to protect citizens and maintain public trust. The service needs to explore new strategies and approaches to address the identified resource constraints. Some of the identified constraints are not the responsibility of the station level alone, it is suggested that strategies must be formulated by management to liaise with the national government and see to it that steps are taken to alleviate these constraints.

7. The police service requires a buy in from policy makers to provide the required funding and resources support to the police. More supervision must be imposed to regulate how the resources are managed and

used. The procurement of the equipment like blue lights, morpho touch machine, bullet proof vests and communication devices must be done timeously to cater for the unforeseen delays in the process. The requisition for new vehicles must be made early in advance. The vehicles ordered must be fit for purpose, for example private cars are sometimes not suitable for visible policing. Vehicles that can travel in uneven terrain chasing suspects and should have enough space to load suspects when caught.

8. To alleviate the staff shortage, burnout, stress, and fatigue that result from work overload, the South African Police Service must advertise and fill the vacant posts as a matter of urgency. Measures must be put in place to assist the police officers that are already absenting themselves from work due to fatigue, stress and burnout caused by work overload, the Employee Assistance Program (EAP) must get involved to assist such police officers. They need to engage the officers to find out the root cause of the challenges faces and come up with working solutions. The employer must put extra efforts aimed at educating the members of the presence of the programs and where to go when the members need their services.

9. The department must invest in officials who will be tasked with identifying gaps in the skills and referring member for training on a need's basis. Training will ensure that the quality of work improves, and errors are reduced. Errors in the work of police officers are very costly as they can lead to miscarriage of justice. For example, if the error is made by the detective in the investigation of a crime scene, it can lead to perpetrators walking free because evidence was not collected and processed correctly. This in turn erode public trust in the work of the police and put the name of the South African Police into disrepute.

10. The study showed that although the identified resources constraints are a major factor in the increase of crime in Hillbrow, however, other factors were also identified as also contributors to the increase in crime levels. These include social issues like street kids, challenges faced by the justice system, municipalities, and home affairs in controlling the influx of illegal immigrants in the country it is found that the resources constraints account for the main challenge in the fight against crime. It is therefore important that whilst efforts are made to alleviate the identified constraints that collaboration is made with other law enforcement agencies, identified stakeholders and community policing forums. Joint efforts are required to fight the scourge of crime in Hillbrow.

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detectives to provide effective policing services. Preventing and solving crime abilities are also negatively affected. It is important for South African Police Service to address these constraints to ensure that they visible police and detectives can carry out their mandate to protect citizens and maintain public trust. The service needs to explore new strategies and approaches to address the identified resource constraints. Some of the identified constraints are not the responsibility of the station level alone, it is suggested that strategies must be formulated by management to liaise with the national government and see to it that steps are taken to alleviate these constraints. The police service requires a buy in from policy makers to provide the required funding and resources support to the police. More supervision must need to be imposed to regulate how the resources are managed and used. The procurement of the equipment like blue lights, morpho touch machine, bullet proof vests and communication devices must be done timeously to cater for the unforeseen delays in the process. The requisition for new vehicles must be made early in advance. The vehicles ordered must be fit for purpose, for example private cars are sometimes not suitable for visible policing. Vehicles that can travel in uneven terrain chasing suspects and should have enough space to load suspects when caught.

To alleviate the staff shortage, burnout, stress, and fatigue that result from work overload, the South African Police Service must advertise and fill the vacant posts as a matter of urgency. Measures must be put in place to assist the police officers that are already absenting themselves from work due to fatigue, stress and burnout caused by work overload, the Employee Assistance Program (EAP) must get involved to assist such police officers. They need to engage the officers to find out the root cause of the challenges faces and come up with working solutions. The employer must put extra efforts aimed at educating the members of the presence of the programs and where to go when the members need their services. The department must invest in officials who will be tasked with identifying gaps in the skills and referring member for training on a need's basis. Training will ensure that the quality of work improves, and errors are reduced. Errors in the work of police officers are very costly as they can lead to miscarriage of justice. For example, if the error is made by the detective in the investigation of a crime scene, it can lead to perpetrators walking free because evidence was not collected and processed correctly. This in turn erode public trust in the work of the police and put the name of the South African Police into disrepute.

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RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To determine the extent of impact of resource constraints on detective and visible policing functions at Hillbrow Police Station, to establish different types of resources which SAPS need to execute their duties, to establish the impact of resource constraints on police work; and to establish ways of increasing productivity using limited resources.

Methodology

Target group/population

The research has been done for Hillbrow Police Station hence fifteen (15) Police Officers and ten (10) stakeholders from community groups for example security companies working with Police were given questionnaires.

Sample and sample type

According to Sarantakos, 2013: 167; Stangor; 2015: 112; "sampling in the quantitative paradigm means taking a portion or a smaller number of units of a population as representative or having particular characteristics of that total population." (Fouché, *et al.*, 2022). Sampling comes in different techniques; non-probability or non-random sampling and probability sampling.

Non-probability sampling includes quota sampling, snowball sampling, judgment sampling and convenience sampling; and the chances of each member making the sample are not known. When population is homogenous, there are high and known probability of each member of the population being selected in a sample; hence probability sampling. As put by Taherdoost, 2016, "probability sampling means that every item in the population has an equal chance of being included in sample." (Taherdoost, 2016). This technique includes simple random, stratified random, cluster sampling, systematic sampling, and multistage sampling. The researcher used random sampling to choose the sample. Fifteen (15) police officers and ten (10) stakeholders were chosen for questionnaires and administered questionnaires. Random sampling is when each member of the population has an equal chance which is independent from other members of being selected in a sample.

DATA COLLECTION

Quantitative data was collected by the researcher. The researcher collected research data through data capturing instruments which are a well-structured research questionnaire for SAPS members and non-SAPS members and statistical analysis to visible policing and detective work at Hillbrow Police Station and various stakeholders to the work of SAPS. Due to the diversity of the study area, the respondents had to come from different departments at Hillbrow Police Station, which are VISPOL, Human Resources and Detectives. The other questionnaire was designed for non-SAPS stakeholders who work with Police in the communities. The research questionnaire (Annexure A) consisted of closed questions that the respondents could answer by selecting from predetermined alternatives and open-

ended questions where respondents provided an explanation.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis is a process where meaning is sort from collected data using various techniques. The research objectives guide the selection of data analysis tools and techniques, questions and the type of data collected. The researcher made use of both qualitative and quantitative data for this research. Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) and MS packages will be used to analyse the data collected from the questionnaires and the SAPS budgets.

FINDINGS

RESPONSES TO THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Out of fifteen (15) members that were given the questionnaire response was received from five (5) detectives and seven (7) visible policing members. Below are the findings.

a) Human Resources - The results showed that the main constraint is personnel. As Hillbrow community has grown significantly, more visible police and detectives are needed. There are staff shortages that are because of members retiring and resigning to joint other professions but have not been replaced. The results further showed that only four (4) shifts in Crime Prevention are servicing over one million community. The shortage has resulted in increased workload for police officers. Where there is an increased workload police officers starts to suffer from fatigue, burnout, stress, and reduced morale. When the members are unwell, this has a negative impact on their output. The constraints facing the detectives in the form of high workload can lead into an increase in crime rate. The detectives are expected to investigate multiple cases with minimum resources available to them. Burnout and Stress result in ill-health which has a negative effect of having a high rate of absenteeism due to long sick leave.

b) Budget Constraints - There are constraints that result from budget cuts on the national level which has a ripple effect in the functioning at provincial level and station level. Budget constraint have affected the personnel turnover, personal protective equipment (PPE), ammunition, evidence kits, pepper prays, dagga weighing scales with calibration certificate, police handheld radios and many more. These have negatively impacted the capacity of visible policing and detectives to conduct investigations.

c) Shortage of vehicles - the findings showed that main resource constraint affecting both visible policing and detectives is the availability motor vehicles that are in good mechanical working order. The station does not have enough supply of vehicles. This result in police officers having to share vehicles and borrow from other shifts. Some vehicles breakdown constantly and the turnaround time can take up to six (6) months due to the backlog at the police garage. This in turn affect visible policing and detective work because if members have no means for transport, they cannot do proper patrolling work or respond to emergency calls. The detectives cannot travel with ease to the crime scenes and to conduct their investigation. The shortage of vehicles leads to a reduction in the number of police

officers on patrol. This in turn negatively affect visible policing. When there is no police visibility, the public confidence in the police decrease and the fear of crime increases.

d) Detectives Skills Training - Some detectives lack the necessary skills in investigation of specific crimes that has increased in the community like, murder, cybercrime, domestic violence and crimes involving children. It is important that detectives are trained adequately in the specialized crime investigation. This training should include crime scene preservation, collection of evidence, preserving evidence, etc. If the detectives are not adequately trained, they become ineffective in their fight against crime. The fight against crime cannot be won if perpetrators are acquitted because of lack of evidence.

e) Lack of proper procurement processes - The results demonstrated that constraints seen in the procurement department has contributed immensely on the challenges faced by both the visible police and detectives. The station currently has a shortage of blue lights in the police vehicles. This hampers the fight against crime because even if a police vehicle s patrolling, community members cannot identify that it's a police vehicle. Blue lights also help to deter crime as criminal will desist from committing crime if they see the presence of police through blue lights. It also makes work of the police officers difficult, especially with stopping and search operations. The other constraints caused by poor procurement processes is that there is no Morpho Touch, fingerprint checking machine which was helping the visible police members to clean out the streets. There is also shortage in the procurement of Bullet Proof Vests. this is putting the safety of police officers at risk when they are outside fighting crime.

f) Technology Constraints - technology constraints also play a big part in the fight against crime. There is a lack of advanced technology at the station level such as forensic labs and surveillance equipment. The detectives must rely on the main lab at the head office which is also having a backlog. This causes the investigation of crime to take too long and leads to reduced public trust.

1. DISCUSSION

Detective Work (Crime investigations)

The purpose of the Detective Services Programme is to enable the investigative work of the SAPS, including providing support to investigators in terms of forensic evidence and criminal records (Unit 2018). Detective work requires investigations to be conducted effectively and it calls for special skills for the police officers. This means one must investigate improving capacity and quality of criminal investigations as identified in the Police Green Paper, "Investigation of crime will not impact positively on crime unless such investigations result in proper detection, successful prosecution, and final conviction. The fight against crime thus rests on two (2) critical aspects; improving the rate of detection and ensuring sanctions are meted out that are commensurate with the type of crime that has been committed. (Civilian Secretariat for Police, 2013). In the end, detective services programme's product is the

successful prosecution of offenders through investigating, gathering and analysing evidence. The programme consists of four (4) main sub-programmes, namely, Crime Investigations, Criminal Record Centre, Forensic Science Laboratory and Specialised Investigations.

Visible Policing

According to the SAPS, the purpose of VISPOL is to: 'Enable police stations to institute and preserve safety and security and provide for specialised interventions and policing of South Africa's borders. Its strategic objective is: 'To discourage all crimes by providing a proactive and responsive policing service that will reduce the levels of priority crimes.' (Service, 2022). Visible policing staff work at Community Service Centres where they engage with the public performing duties like crime prevention awareness campaigns, opening case dockets, social crime prevention, certifying documents, filing accident reports, attending station complaints (serving protection orders), management of station cells, stores, and firearms. They also perform duties related to security at courts, checking compliance of liquor outlets and second-hand goods; sector patrols and management of emergency response services (10111) and adopt a cop in school's programme. Visible policing entails the visible performance of duties as well as the regular and discernible presence of the police in public spaces (Civilian Secretariat for Police, 2013). Visible policing through patrols and community policing are methods which are effective in being proactive in prevention of crime and as such an important area wherein SAPS should have the ability to: "control their own internal management, including the distribution and use of resources. This includes managing the quantity and quality of personnel and equipment assigned to various locations and functions for maximum efficiency. (Civilian Secretariat for Police, 2013). The importance of visible policing is also raised by Sherman (1998a: 239) who highlights, directed patrols, proactive arrests and problem solving in high crime areas ("hot spots") have shown substantial evidence of crime prevention. (Burger, 2018).

To meet the mandate of SAPS in an effective way, resource allocation in SAPS has followed several methodologies over the years which include the Mannekrag Plan, the Resource Allocation Guide (RAG), the Resource Establishment Plan, and the Theoretical Human Resource Requirement (THRR). For the purposes of this research, the author focuses on the currently used method; the Theoretical Human Resource Requirement (THRR). Crime rates is closely related to Organizational Structure of SAPS, including the hierarchy, departments, and specialized units, which influence the human resource requirements. The number of officers required for administrative roles, investigative units, specialized units (such as narcotics, cybercrime, or traffic), and operational roles must be considered depending on nature of crime and frequency.

Workload and Shift Patterns - The workload and shift patterns of police officers also impact the human resource requirement. Factors like average working hours, rest days, and leave policies need to be considered to ensure adequate coverage and avoid officer

burnout. It's important to note that determining the theoretical human resource requirement is a complex process that requires detailed analysis, including input from experts, law enforcement professionals, and policymakers. It involves striking a balance between available resources, budget constraints, and the desired level of public safety.

Limitations

- Some of the sources used by the researcher will be out of the ten (10) year range when final report is submitted.
- Although reference is often made to SAPS in the research, this study is limited to the SAPS Hillbrow Police Station from which a sample of respondents was selected. Therefore, the conclusions made in this study may not sufficiently have been informed by the experiences of employees that are stationed other police stations.
- Furthermore, this study is limited to a particular timeframe 2018 - 2021, part of the period during which Covid-19 resulted in Government funding being redirected to cater for the pandemic hence the budgets might not necessarily reflect what might have been without the pandemic.

CONCLUSION

Resource constraints in SAPS have a significant impact on visible policing and detective work at Hillbrow Police Station. South Africa faces numerous crime related challenges which include high levels of violent crime, organized crime, cybercrime, violence against women and children, and widespread corruption. The research demonstrated that there is shortage in human resource, there are budget constraints, shortage of vehicles, gaps in the training of detective skills, lack of working procurement processes and technology problems in the national forensic laboratory. All these factors limit the ability of the visible police and detectives to provide effective policing services. Preventing and solving crime abilities are also negatively affected.

It is important for South African Police Service to address these constraints to ensure that the Uniformed police and detectives are able to carry out their mandate to protect citizens and maintain public trust. The service needs to explore new strategies and approaches to address the identified resource constraints. Some of the identified constraints are not the responsibility of the station level alone, it is suggested that strategies must be formulated by management to liaise with the national government and see to it that steps are taken to alleviate these constraints.

The police service requires a buy in from policy makers to provide the required funding and resources support to the police. More supervision must need to be imposed to regulate how the resources are managed and used. The procurement of the equipment like blue lights, morpho touch machine, bullet proof vests and communication devices must be done timeously to cater for the unforeseen delays in the process. The requisition for new vehicles must be made early in advance. The vehicles ordered must be fit for purpose, for example private cars are sometimes not suitable for visible policing. Vehicles that can travel in uneven terrain

chasing suspects and should have enough space to load suspects when caught.

To alleviate the staff shortage, burnout, stress, and fatigue that result from work overload, the South African Police Service must advertise and fill the vacant posts as a matter of urgency. Measures must be put in place to assist the police officers that are already absenting themselves from work due to fatigue, stress and burnout caused by work overload, the Employee Assistance Program (EAP) must get involved to assist such police officers. They need to engage the officers to find out the root cause of the challenges faces and come up with working solutions. The employer must put extra efforts aimed at educating the members of the presence of the programs and where to go when the members need their services. The department must invest in officials who will be tasked with identifying gaps in the skills and referring member for training on a need's basis. Training will ensure that the quality of work improves, and errors are reduced. Errors in the work of police officers are very costly as they can lead to miscarriage of justice. For example, if the error is made by the detective in the investigation of a crime scene, it can lead to perpetrators walking free because evidence was not collected and processed correctly. This in turn erode public trust in the work of the police and put the name of the South African Police into disrepute. The study showed that although the identified resources constraints are a major factor in the increase of crime in Hillbrow, however, other factors were also identified as also contributors to the increase in crime levels. These include social issues like street kids, challenges faced by the justice system, municipalities, and home affairs in controlling the influx of illegal immigrants in the country it is found that the resources constraints account for the main challenge in the fight against crime. It is therefore important that whilst efforts are made to alleviate the identified constraints that collaboration is made with other law enforcement agencies, identified stakeholders and community policing forums. Joint efforts are required to fight the scourge of crime in Hillbrow.

References

1. Fouché, C., Strydom, H. & Roestenburg, W. (2022). *Research at grass roots*. (Seventh (7th) ed.) Pretoria: Van Schalk.
2. Taherdoost, H. (2016). *Sampling Methods in Research Methodology; How to Choose a Sampling Technique for Research*. *International Journal of Academic Research in Management (IJARM)*, 5(2), 18 - 27.
3. Civilian Secretariat for Police. (2013). *Green Paper on Policing*, Pretoria, July.
4. Parveen, H. & Showkat, N. (2017). 'Research Ethics', e-PG Pathshala, July.
5. Nagia-Luddy, J. R. & F. (2015). "Unconscionable and irrational: SAPS Human Resource allocation"; *SA Crime Quarterly*.
6. De Vos, A. S., Strydom H. F. C. & Delport, D. C. (2011). *Research at Grass Roots*, fourth (4th) ed, Van Schaik.

7. Salkind, N. J. (2012). *Research Methodology for the Economic and Management Sciences*. Eight (8th) edn, Pearson: Cape town.

8. Husselmann, K. (2017). "Colloquium:Evaluation of the Current Resource Allocation Model in the South African Police Service", unpublished manuscript, s.l.: s.n.

9. Service, T. S. M. C. S. A. P, (2020). "Strategic Plan South African Police Service 2020 to 2025, Pretoria: s.n.

10. Burger, J. (n.d.) (2018). *Strategic Perspectives on Crime and Policing in South Africa*, first (1st) edn, thirteen (13th) Impression, Pretoria: Van Schaik.

11. English Oxford Living Dictionaries. (2018). Oxford University Press. Available at: <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/> [Date of accessed on: 10 March 2023] Unit, P. O. S. A. R., (2018). 2018/19 BUDGET AND ANNUAL PERFORMANCE PLAN (APP) ANALYSIS OF VOTE 23: DEPARTMENT OF POLICE, CapeTown: s.n.

12. South African Police Service (2021) *Police Magazine 2021*, [online]. Available at: <https://www.saps.gov.za/resource-centre/publications/police-mag/pol-2021.pdf> [Accessed on: 16 June 2023].